

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

Documented Use Cases - 1st Batch

Title of Deliverable:	Documented Use Cases - 1st Batch		
Deliverable Number:	D3.3		
Type of Data:	Report		
Lead Beneficiary:	University of Münster		
Publishing Status	Public		
Last Revision Date:	30/03/2024	by:	Lena Mausbach, Daniel Scheuermann, Alexandra Nusser, Michiel De Clerck, Lieneke Timpers
Verification Date:	31/03/2024	by:	Francesca Cadeddu
Approval Date:	[DD/MM/YYYY]	by:	[Name]
Document Name:	RESILIENCE_WP3_D3.3_Documented Use Cases - 1st Batch_FINAL		

Funded by
the European Union

Change History

Version Number	Date	Status	Name	Summary of Main Changes
00.01	17/03/2024	DRAFT	Initial Draft	
00.02	20/03/2024	WORKING	First Revised Text	Feedback Reviewers
00.03	29/03/2024	WORKING	Second Revised Text	Feedback BoD
01.00	30/03/2024	FINAL	Final Version	

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Distribution List

Name	Beneficiary	Role
RESILIENCE consortium	all	
Public		

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Refining of Archetypes.....	7
2.1. The User-Oriented Approach of RESILIENCE.....	7
2.2. User Groups and Archetypes: Development of the Focus.....	8
2.3. Outlook on Future Proceedings	12
3. Use Cases	13
3.1. User Stories as Basis for the Use Cases	13
3.2. Definition of the Use Cases	14
3.3. Six Use Cases and their SMART Goals	16
3.3.1. Use Case Template Accessibility 1.....	17
3.3.2. Use Case Template Accessibility 2.....	19
3.3.3. Use Case Template Accessibility 3.....	21
3.3.4. Use Case Template Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access.....	23
3.3.5. Use Case Template Research Data Management	24
3.3.6. Use Case Template Scientific Support/Empowerment	26
4. Conclusion and Next Steps	29
5. Reference Documents	30

List of Figures

Figure 1: Archetypes and Services	9
Figure 2: User Archetypes and Description	10
Figure 3: Academic Discipline of the Interviewees from the Workshop Proceedings 1st Batch M1-21	11
Figure 4: Quantitative Results of the Expressed User Needs from the Content Analysis of the Interviews	13

List of Tables

Table 1: The Evolution from User Needs to User Stories to Use Cases.....	15
Table 2: Use Case Template Accessibility 1.....	18
Table 3: Use Case Template Accessibility 2.....	20
Table 4: Use Case Template Accessibility 3	22
Table 5: Use Case Template Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access	24
Table 6: Use Case Template Research Data Management	26
Table 7: Use Case Template Scientific Support/Empowerment.....	28

1. Introduction

RESILIENCE as a European cross-disciplinary research infrastructure for research on religion in all academic fields prioritises its future users and their needs. WP3 aims to survey the user requirements as comprehensively as possible, so that the research infrastructure (RI) will be able to offer those services that are requested or envisioned by the community. WP3 is tasked with organising workshops in cooperation with WP4 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) in which the RI and its possibilities are presented to the focus groups. WP2 has also collaborated on this task from the outset, as the collection of user requirements (WP3) and the strategic planning and the preparation of the services (WP2) must be closely coordinated. The aim of these workshops is to find out the requirements of the users in detail, to understand the needs of the future end users, to find out what their priorities are, to align the development of the services accordingly and to map existing services. From the basis of the first batch of workshops and user stories collected from these (see D3.1 and D3.5), it is the additional task of the WP to refine the eight archetype users' profiles that have been already presented in the RESILIENCE User Strategy.¹ Based on a list of prioritised services (see T3.1), the intention is that the users lay the foundation for the use cases by presenting their perspective and requirements for each service in the interviews. At a later stage, this input is to be prototyped and presented back to the end-users for User Interface/User experience validation sessions whenever a new service goes in development.

This deliverable presents the foundations for these further developments in three chapters. First, the evolution of the archetypes is presented and the decisions that led to the redefinition are explained. In a second step, the use cases based on the user stories will be showcased. In this chapter, the use case template will be presented and applied to three use cases for three future services providing "Data access: discoverability of data sources" that answers the user need for "Accessibility" (3.3.1-3.3.3), one use case for an existing service (TNA) will be presented that

¹ Cf. the deliverable D2.3 from the Design Phase — Grant 871127 — RESILIENCE High-Level User Strategy Report (RESILIENCE_WP2_USR_01.00_FINAL), confidential, available upon request.

addresses the need for “Networking” (3.3.4), one for “Research Data Management” (3.3.5) and another one for the future service “Help Desk” that fulfils the need for “Scientific support/Empowerment” (3.3.6). Finally, S.M.A.R.T objectives are formulated in relation to the user/functional requirements, that will then represent the future work focus.

2. Refining of Archetypes

2.1. The User-Oriented Approach of RESILIENCE

As RESILIENCE places its future users at the core of its activities, the approach to its preparation is primarily user oriented. In the project's Design Phase four main user target groups have been identified, analysed, and described in detail:² 1. Researchers, 2. Collection managers, librarians and archivists (GLAM³ sector), 3. Decision makers, and 4. Workers in religious communities. Through surveys conducted during the Design Phase RESILIENCE split the main four user groups into eight archetypes of potential users that enable custom-fit service design.

As the Design-Thinking-Process, which led to these results, is an agile process, it is one of the tasks of WP3 to further refine these Archetypes. Input for the process was gained (1) via a number of workshops, the interviews conducted during those workshops, and the workshop evaluations, and (2) through consultation within the WP and exchange of these results with the other WPs of the Consortium. The most crucial part of this process, the workshop on user requirements, was developed by WP3 in collaboration with WP2 and WP4 in the first months of the RESILIENCE PPP. The workshops have been carried out in cooperation with partners from the consortium at four locations (Status February 2024) and will be conducted further throughout the project phase. The workshop concept aims in the first place to collect and prioritise user requirements through the individual and group interviews; additionally, it presents RESILIENCE to potential users of the RI. As shown in D3.5 "User Stories Catalogue - 1st Batch"⁴ and D3.1 "Workshops Proceedings - 1st Batch"⁵, the WP was able to collect a wide range of data from the conducted workshop about the users, which lead to meaningful insights in the user requirements of researchers and librarians especially in Southeastern Europe. The analysis of the data and feedback has shown that three key needs stand out for the researchers: Accessibility (with 88 statements, which corresponds to 15%),

² Cf. the deliverable D2.3 from the Design Phase — Grant 871127 — RESILIENCE High-Level User Strategy Report (RESILIENCE_WP2_USR_01.00_FINAL), confidential.

³ Abbreviation "GLAM": Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums.

⁴ [RESILIENCE_WP3_D3.5_User-Stories-Catalogue-1st-Batch_01.00_FINAL.pdf \(resilience-ri.eu\)](#).

⁵ [RESILIENCE_WP3_D3.1_WorkshopProceedings1_01.00_FINAL.pdf \(resilience-ri.eu\)](#).

Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access (with 80 statements, corresponding 14%), and Research Data Management (60 statements - 10%). These were confirmed over and over by the interviewed researchers, who also viewed positively the potential contribution of RESILIENCE to these needs.

2.2. User Groups and Archetypes: Development of the Focus

The eight archetypes identified during the RESILIENCE Design Phase are presented in figure 1. They were chosen to enable an empathic perspective towards the needs of the community, demonstrate use cases, and lead to custom-tailored service design.

The 8 Archetypes of RESILIENCE Users and their Need for Services

Figure 1: Archetypes and Services

FRANCESCO – I am a PhD researcher in Religious Studies and for my thesis I am searching for literature and manuscripts, which are digitised or only physically accessible. Some of these manuscripts I need are not available digitally or physically at my institution, but I find them in other RESILIENCE institutions. The RESILIENCE TNA scholarship allows me to travel to access these manuscripts and to fund my research on site. At the same time RESILIENCE helps me to get in contact with other researchers in my field and experts from the GLAM sector for the resources I need to use. In the future I can imagine publishing the common research results in an Open Access Journal.

MAJA – I am a university professor in the field of Religious Studies. When I was younger, I worked in the humanities as an individual researcher, but now I am expected to manage larger research teams to investigate broader phenomena. RESILIENCE Collaboration Services helped me to define the scope of my future project with other experts and find new international collaborators from beyond my usual professional network. For the purpose of my future project, I need to work more with datasets, not only single texts, so I will require RESILIENCE consultancy in DH methods and management of the research data. Being still busy with my other duties, I plan to send one of my PhD students to participate in the research infrastructure's training programme. By including her into the train-the-trainer framework, I expect both to raise her individual skills and provide the knowledge transfer to my entire team.

ÉTIENNE – Passionate about journalism and photography, after getting my PhD in History, I started working as a freelance reporter on immigration and ethno-nationalist conflicts in Europe. As a strong identity factor, religion is often a center point in these conflicts and, therefore, an ever present topic in my projects. In that, RESILIENCE really makes my day! Thanks to the infrastructure, I can access precise knowledge and scientific data on religion and get in touch with experts. Finding reliable information about the different topics I work on is made easier by RESILIENCE Search & Find services. As a journalist, and a researcher, I found RESILIENCE is an indispensable treasure.

TAMAR – As a sociologist, I am analysing the phenomena of religions with an empiric approach. I need to create and use datasets, which can become difficult, because the right datasets, which often already exist somewhere, are sometimes hard to find and access. Within the RESILIENCE Research Enhancing and Research Enabling services, the (re-)usage of such datasets becomes easier for me. For the data I create for my own research, I use now the RESILIENCE Research Data Management services, which finally provides a suitable long-term solution for the various formats I need to store. Sometimes I need to process different datasets which have no common ontologies and are not interoperable. RESILIENCE offers me the opportunity to work on that problem and consults with me about possible solutions.

DMITRIS – I work in a local community archive, including archival funds of religious communities. The RESILIENCE trainings have helped me to describe these sources according to international standards and making them known to international researchers. If in a later phase I use the research infrastructure's resources to provide researchers with digitized versions of these sources, I appeal to the RESILIENCE Helpdesk Service to make my work as sustainable as possible. When later, I see the results of these researchers' studies of my archives popping up in the RESILIENCE newsletters, I always feel proud. As such, when the sources in my archives find their place in a European narrative, I know I have succeeded in letting my work for my local community serve the international community as well.

DUNJA – I am a librarian in the National Library and in my everyday activities I provide access to a range of reading resources including those of religion and Religious Studies. Working in an electronic environment I need to improve my technological skills to use the new media and new services that the library will acquire to complete building both the e-library and the digital library. To maximize my output and to handle properly technological tools, my managerial skills need to be enhanced too. (RESILIENCE Trainings). We work closely with museums, schools and other public bodies and we often organize events to promote the use of the library, to expand our network and to gain access to data from other institutions. Collaboration services of RESILIENCE enable me to get in touch with international experts who can broaden my perspective on the collections that I am in custody of and also to invite them to actually use and investigate the resources of my institution, particularly the special collections.

ELIN – In my job I need to evaluate and compare didactical concepts in different regions. Religious and cultural diversity become more and more the lived reality of the students and teachers I am working with. Nevertheless, there is often a lack of solid information about different religious matters, which needs to be considered on a structural educational level. Therefore I often have to fight prejudices, act as a mediator and educate responsible people in the educational sector about religious diversity and how to integrate inclusive concepts. For myself I am therefore continuously looking for datasets and publications using RESILIENCE Search & Find services and sometimes direct Physical Access of the infrastructure to literature on site. Sometimes, it really helps to get directly in touch with experts for religious issues and consult with them. RESILIENCE Collaboration services helps with that a lot and makes it easy to find the right expert.

MARIA – I am a curator at an internationally renowned museum. The exhibition I am curating is related to the history of religions in Europe, therefore RESILIENCE offers an excellent starting point for my research. Searching on the platform, I easily find for example digitised artifacts I can use for the multimedia part of my exhibition. The services also offer clear licensing information so we know how to use the materials. Within RESILIENCE, I get not only access to research data but also an overview of current research debates. RESILIENCE also helps me to get in contact with other GLAM institutions and internationally renowned experts working on the same topics.

Figure 2: User Archetypes and Description

The archetypes presented in the Design Phase are refined in the RESILIENCE PPP as part of Task T3.2; WP3 has therefore been especially concerned with their validity and applicability from the very beginning of the project. Starting with a focus group with members of WP2 at the Innovation Meeting of WU and WP Leaders in Palermo (29/08/-02/09/2023), WP3 has addressed the task of the refinement several times.

RESILIENCE is a research infrastructure for all academic fields related to the study of religion, so WP3 decided to focus initially on the prioritised user group of researchers.⁶ This choice aligns with the aim of RESILIENCE to integrate existing services. The already active services offered by RESILIENCE in the current PPP are the [Transnational Access \(TNA\) Fellowship Programme](#), the [Religious Studies Discovery Environment RelReSearch](#) and [Trainings](#). These services can be assigned to the user groups researchers and - via the expansion of the TNA hosts - also to the GLAM sector. It can be assumed that these are the two user groups that have so far benefited most from these existing services. In addition to this previous assignment, it is of course still the task to find out not only the RI options for these user groups but take the other previously defined groups into account and to check the applicability of RESILIENCE services to their specific needs.

Figure 3: Academic Discipline of the Interviewees from the Workshop Proceedings 1st Batch M1-21

⁶ Cf. [RESILIENCE’s Vision and Mission Statement](#).

2.3. Outlook on Future Proceedings

As it was shown, the efforts of the WP are currently focused on the two prioritised user groups (researchers and members of the GLAM sector). However, efforts are also being made to gain and apply insights into the other two user groups (i.e. decision makers and workers in religious communities) from the data collected. This means that the interviews conducted so far are also analysed in regards to their informative value about the other user groups. In doing so, the WP can follow the specifications of the vision and mission statement⁷ but does not lose sight of the preliminary work of the Design Phase. This approach is the basis for future tasks and also structures the next steps defined in D3.1. This means on the one hand, that in the following workshops (in accordance to 3.2), which are already planned for the upcoming months (Sarajevo, Warsaw, Zurich, Paris, tba), the interview questionnaire for the GLAM user group will be used in addition to the guideline which was developed for interviewing researchers (see appendix). The data collection will be furthermore enriched in the future by individual interviews that all partners are intended to conduct until the end of M30. This addition of data can also be included in the refinement of archetypes and user groups

The prioritisation and selection of services is being worked on in close coordination with WP2. UI/UX mock-ups will be created at each stage when new core services are scheduled for implementation in order to test the respective service and obtain user feedback to ensure that the prototypes meet the needs and expectations of the users. The team responsible for developing a specific new developed core service should start with a rudimentary mockup based on the use case for said service. These mockups can be further refined based on user input and feedback after which the service can be developed. The different iterations of the service in development can then be used to collect further input. This procedure could also be at the disposal to the in-kind developments in order to support the harmonisation between the two "layers" or types of services.

⁷ Cf. RESILIENCE's Vision and Mission Statement: [Vision, Mission, and Values – Serving Research, Building Knowledge, Version 02.00](#)

3. Use Cases

3.1. User Stories as Basis for the Use Cases

The basis for the selection and definition of the use cases for this first batch are the user stories presented in D3.5 User Stories Catalogue - 1st Batch. These user stories represent requirements collected from the user perspective in 23 individual interviews and four group interviews. The results of the evaluation of these user stories in D3.5 are structured as follows:

Figure 4: Quantitative Results of the Expressed User Needs from the Content Analysis of the Interviews

The basis of the use cases is formed by the user stories, which describe the need for future services from the users' perspective in accordance with the user-oriented approach of the project. In the user stories, the complexity of the user requirements was first broken down into individual requirements that can be precisely related to the necessary services.

In the user stories, future users have described their goals with regard to their use of the RI. On this basis, the use cases define how these goals can be achieved in their technical implementation. They therefore focus on the human perspective: How can a person who uses a certain service achieve the goal? In technical terms it is a description of the interaction between the system and its users, which provides the developers of the RI and its services with a good understanding of the work that must be done. To document the steps of a user to achieve a goal, the WP decided to use a so-called "use case template". This template was applied to four user stories from D3.5 that led to six use cases: three on accessibility and one each on networking/mobility/transnational access, research data management and scientific support.

3.2. Definition of the Use Cases

The most frequently mentioned user needs in quantitative terms were "Accessibility" (with 15% of the responses), "Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access" (14%) and "Research Data Management" (10%), closely followed by "Scientific Support" (8%)⁸, for which six use cases have been defined. The aim of this approach is to create a list of specific services based on the data and insights from the interviews, which will guide WP2 in selecting services and prioritising their implementation.

⁸ The user needs for "Software/Tools" (10%) and "Enhancement of Research" (9%) are not yet addressed here, as the development of the corresponding services is not scheduled for this project phase.

User Needs	User Stories	Use Case Title
Accessibility	As a researcher, I want a wide range of access to digitised literature, so that the scope of my research is not reduced by a lack of travel options.	Data access: discoverability of data sources (3.3.1, 3.3.2 and 3.3.3)
Networking	As a researcher, I want to have a contact person at the place I am visiting, so I can get instructed on the use of libraries, catalogues etc.	Transnational Access (3.3.4)
Research Data Management	As a researcher, I want my data to be sustainably stored, so it stays available and usable after the finalisation of a project.	Data storage according to FAIR principles (3.3.5)
Scientific Support	As a collection manager, I want to have content-related support by experts in the field of Religious Studies, so that I can optimise the standard and variety of our collection	Help Desk: Support for collection managers (3.3.6)

Table 1: The Evolution from User Needs to User Stories to Use Cases

3.3. Six Use Cases and their SMART Goals

In this chapter, **six use cases with the user/functional requirements** are developed. The **use case template** contains the following categories:

- Each is based on a **User story** derived from the interviews.
- After determining the **User group** (e.g. researchers or members of the GLAM sector), the use case is named in the **Title** and given a **Description**.
- The **Primary Actor** is the service/tool that answers the need.
- The **Preconditions** outline the state the system is in before the use case begins, that is the situation in which the user finds her/himself with a need they need to resolve, and the **Postconditions** characterise the intended state that has arisen through the use of the service, that is the state the system is in after one of the use case pathway is completed.
- The **Main Success Scenario** describes the steps a user goes through in a use case where nothing goes wrong.
- **Constraints/Issues/Risks** and the **Frequency of Use** are anticipated.
- The **Status** indicates the degree of implementation of the service, the **Owner** of the service is specified, and the **Priority** of its implementation is categorised into high, medium or low.

For each of these use cases, **SMART goals** for the current and/or for the next project phase are defined. SMART objectives are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-bound. They are structured in the following way: "The goal [quantifiable objective] will be achieved by [timeframe in the operational phase of RESILIENCE]. [Key players] will accomplish this goal by [what steps will be taken to achieve the goal]."

3.3.1. Use Case Template Accessibility 1

User story:	As a researcher, I want a wide range of access to digitised literature, so that the scope of my research is not reduced by a lack of travel options.
User group:	Researchers
Title:	Data access: discoverability of data sources (1)
Description:	<p>Context: Researchers require access to all types of digitalized research data and literature that is available online because this material in its non-digitized form is often unique or not widely available. Accessing the material in its non-digitized form would require travelling to a variety of locations, which is not necessarily feasible. There are still, however, obstacles to the access to digitised materials as well: data silos, paid subscriptions, institutional credentials, lack of discoverability, etc.</p> <p>Goal: Although issues related to subscription licences and other explicit access restrictions cannot be resolved (except by the entities that set the access restrictions), it is possible to make data that is available under open access licences more accessible. There is a lot of potentially useful research data that can be made more accessible via 3 paths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making data sources and other platforms that house research data or publications more easily discoverable - Aggregating datasets from several providers on one data hub/discovery platform - Providing a data publishing and sharing solution that allows researchers to share the materials that they have the rights to share
Primary Actor:	A catalogue for data sources where they can be adequately described to serve as a point of departure in finding the necessary research materials.
Preconditions:	A researcher searches for the topic they are interested in.

Postconditions:	A researcher has found a data repository/publishing platform/digital collection/... that provides them with access to the research materials they need.
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researcher searches or browses for topic - Researcher finds several potential results - Researcher looks at the descriptions on the catalogue to find out which results are relevant - Researcher goes to the dedicated platforms they find and uses them
Constraints/Issues/Risks:	<p>Researchers do not find what they are looking for because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - it does not exist - it is not available in open access - it is not included on the catalogue - the description of the resource is not adequate
Frequency of Use:	The earliest stages of research when literature/primary sources/ research data is collected
Status:	Templates for the description of resources are ready.
Owner:	RESILIENCE WP2
Priority:	High

Table 2: Use Case Template Accessibility 1

SMART Goal: Information about 10 more data sources relevant to the Religious Studies community will be collected. That information will be presented on the RESILIENCE service catalogue by 2026. This will be achieved by WP2 by analysing the information provided by partners about possible data sources and presenting that information on an online platform where researchers can browse and find the data sources they need.

3.3.2. Use Case Template Accessibility 2

User story:	As a researcher, I want a wide range of access to digitised literature, so that the scope of my research is not reduced by a lack of travel options.
User group:	Researchers
Title:	Data access: discoverability of data sources (2)
Description:	<p>Context: Researchers require access to all types of digitalised research data and literature that is available online because this material in its non-digitised form is often unique or not widely available. Accessing the material in its non-digitised form would require travelling to a variety of locations, which is not necessarily feasible. There are still, however, obstacles to the access to digitised materials as well: data silos, paid subscriptions, institutional credentials, lack of discoverability, etc.</p> <p>Goal: Although issues related to subscription licences and other explicit access restrictions cannot be resolved (except by the entities that set the access restrictions), it is possible to make data that is available under open access licences more accessible. There is a lot of potentially useful research data that can be made more accessible via 3 paths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making data sources and other platforms that house research data or publications more easily discoverable. - Aggregating datasets from several providers on one data hub/discovery platform. - Providing a data publishing and sharing solution that allows researchers to share the materials that they have the rights to share.
Primary Actor:	A data hub and discovery platform
Preconditions:	A user searches for specific research materials.
Postconditions:	The user finds useful research materials
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researcher searches or browses for records (books/articles/...) - Researcher finds several potential results

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The researchers exports the results/copies citations to the results OR - Researcher clicks the link to the provider platform to continue their search there
Constraints/Issues/Risks:	<p>Researchers do not find what they are looking for because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - it does not exist - it is not available on ReIReSearch - the record does not have sufficient descriptive metadata to be findable <p>Researchers find what they are looking for but the results are not available because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the provider platform is unavailable - dead links - no digital representation of the record requires them to travel after all
Frequency of Use:	The earliest stages of research when literature/primary sources/ research data is collected.
Status:	ReIReSearch is operational.
Owner:	RESILIENCE WP2
Priority:	Low

Table 3: Use Case Template Accessibility 2

SMART Goal: 10 more data sources relevant to religious studies per year will be added to the RESILIENCE data hub and discovery platform ReIReSearch in the next phase of RESILIENCE (2026-2030). This will be achieved by WP2 by onboarding the data sources to ReIReSearch.

3.3.3. Use Case Template Accessibility 3

User story:	As a researcher, I want a wide range of access to digitised literature, so that the scope of my research is not reduced by a lack of travel options.
User group:	Researchers
Title:	Data access: discoverability of data sources (3)
Description:	<p>Context: Researchers require access to all types of digitalised research data and literature that is available online because this material in its non-digitised form is often unique or not widely available. Accessing the material in its non-digitised form would require travelling to a variety of locations, which is not necessarily feasible. There are still, however, obstacles to the access to digitised materials as well: data silos, paid subscriptions, institutional credentials, lack of discoverability, etc.</p> <p>Goal: Although issues related to subscription licences and other explicit access restrictions cannot be resolved (except by the entities that set the access restrictions), it is possible to make data that is available under open access licences more accessible. There is a lot of potentially useful research data that can be made more accessible via 3 paths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making data sources and other platforms that house research data or publications more easily discoverable. - Aggregating datasets from several providers on one data hub/discovery platform. - Providing a data publishing and sharing solution that allows researchers to share the materials that they have the rights to share.
Primary Actor:	Zenodo: a research data sharing platform. It can be used both for finding and sharing data.
Preconditions:	A researcher searches for the materials they are interested in.
Postconditions:	Researcher finds the research data/publication/presentation/etc. they need.

Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researcher searches or browses for records - Researcher finds several potential results - Researcher downloads the corresponding files
Constraints/Issues /Risks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No relevant data available on Zenodo - Relevant records exist but the actual files are not available in open access.
Frequency of Use:	<p>The earliest stages of research when literature/primary sources/ research data is collected.</p> <p>The end of the research cycle when data/publications can be shared.</p>
Status:	A RESILIENCE community exists in Zenodo but is not yet being promoted/used.
Owner:	RESILIENCE WP2
Priority:	Medium

Table 4: Use Case Template Accessibility 3

SMART Goal: Ten new entries of Religious Studies research data and results will be submitted per year to the RESILIENCE Zenodo Community in the next phase of RESILIENCE (2026-2028). This will be achieved by WP2 by encouraging and training researchers on how to publish their data in a FAIR way in the RESILIENCE Zenodo community.

3.3.4. Use Case Template Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access

User story:	As a researcher, I want to have a contact person at the place I am visiting, so I can get instructed on the use of libraries, catalogues etc.
User group:	Junior and mid-career level researchers: PhD, Post-doctoral researchers, assistant professor, associate professor, and all their academic equivalents.
Title:	Transnational Access
Description:	Facilitate visiting scholar exchange research stays at Higher Institutes of Education, libraries, archives and other institutes that include the study of religion in their scope of research, collection(s), and activities.
Primary Actor:	Effective and operating TNA Infrastructure with sufficient hosts in all European countries with access to all important physical and digital resources for research on religion.
Preconditions:	No access to specific sources, collections, libraries, or archives necessary to achieve and/or conduct their research; OR missing expertise and/or training in specific tools, software or catalogues to access the knowledge or research methodology needed for their research.
Postconditions:	Having had access to the specific sources, expertise and/or training, the quality of the research (e.g. better methodology, more streamlined data management, higher quality output) has improved to an extent not possible without the TNA Fellowship programme.
Main Success Scenario:	The TNA Fellow applies for a TNA Fellowship during the Call for TNA Fellowships with a project proposal and the required sources, training, and/or expertise needed to improve or complete (a part of) their research. They are accepted by the TNA Host, who ensures that the agreed on and required sources, expertise, and training will be available to the TNA Fellow on arrival. The TNA Fellow makes use of the offered package and completes that part of the research that is dependent on access to the TNA Host's facilities, and writes a short report (to be used for communication purposes) to summarise their experiences. After the research stay the TNA Fellow completes an evaluation of the full experience as feedback for both the Host and

	the RESILIENCE TNA Programme. The TNA Fellow reports back on all academic publications made possible by the research visit.
Constraints/Issues /Risks:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TNA Fellow application is denied by the TNA Host 2. Visit postponed or cancelled by the TNA Fellow 3. Visit postponed or cancelled by the TNA Host 4. The offer of the TNA Host is incomplete or insufficient for the research needs of the TNA Fellow
Frequency of Use:	Provide ongoing and efficient access for all researchers who require a TNA stay to carry out their research project on religion.
Status:	Unfunded pilot programme until June 2026 with operating infrastructure of 15 TNA Hosts.
Owner:	RESILIENCE WP2
Priority:	High

Table 5: Use Case Template Networking/Mobility/Transnational Access

SMART Goal: The RESILIENCE TNA Programme will be maintained and extended with 2 new hosts per year/15 TNA fellows per year/2 calls per year in the next phase of RESILIENCE (2026-2036). This will be achieved through WU Transnational Access (WP2) by continuing the established procedure as well as applying for funding. The figures represent the minimum scenario if the funds are not increased.

3.3.5. Use Case Template Research Data Management

User story:	As a researcher, I want my data to be sustainably stored, so it stays available and usable after the finalisation of a project.
User group:	Researchers
Title:	Data storage according to FAIR principles

Description:	<p>Context: Researchers require a service for RDM as it is an essential prerequisite for the digital preservation, reusability and archiving of scientific data. To ensure data storage after FAIR guidelines, data management plans and trusted repositories have to be made available by the RI for the users. Through the data management aligned with FAIR- Principles, the researchers will be empowered to support other researchers through their data.</p> <p>Goal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coordinated RDM - open access to research data - unintentional data loss or misuse can be avoided
Primary Actor:	Service Centre for Research Data Management
Preconditions:	A researcher wants their data to be FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
Postconditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RDM covers the entire life cycle from project planning to data generation, data storage, metadata description and documentation, also including conscious decision as to which data from the research process should be preserved in the long term. - All ethical and legal framework conditions are taken into account
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers can achieve and guarantee Reusability and archiving of scientific data by FAIR RDM. - Safe and reliable storage of files and data for researchers. - Through good research data management, the researcher can show evidence of independent scientific work as well as a methodologically correct procedure in accordance with the guidelines for ensuring good scientific practice (f.ex. from DFG).
Constraints/Issues /Risks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of consistency in the conceptualization and implementation of RDM - Complexity of RDM practices in general - Researchers might find RDM too time-consuming
Frequency of Use:	The earliest stages of a research project; Subsequent maintenance for already existing data

Status:	The Service Centre for Research Data Management is already operating
Owner:	University of Münster
Priority:	Medium

Table 6: Use Case Template Research Data Management

SMART Goal: The RESILIENCE research community will consolidate the cooperation with the Service Centre for Research Data Management at the University of Münster. It is aimed at storing the research data on the Service Centre’s repository in the next phase of RESILIENCE (2026-2028). This will be achieved by WP3 by offering storage capacities at the Service Centre for Research Data Management.

3.3.6. Use Case Template Scientific Support/Empowerment

User story:	As a collection manager, I want to have content-related support by experts in the field of Religious Studies, so that I can optimise the standard and variety of our collection.
User group:	Members of the GLAM sector: Collection managers and librarians who are experts for digital and physical archives, databases, collections. They provide researchers with requested sources and support them in their daily work.
Title:	Help Desk — Support for collection managers

<p>Description:</p>	<p>Context: A collection manager wants to optimise the standard of her library's collection on a particular topic. Because she herself is not an expert in this subject area, she researches the topic extensively and tries to identify the standard literature and current debates.</p> <p>Goal: Even if the research cannot be replaced and the collection manager has to select the appropriate literature for her location, a help desk can facilitate the research in several ways:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Help Desk Manager puts the collection manager in contact with experts in the subject area. 2) Help Desk Manager brings the collection manager into contact with libraries that specialised literature to this topic.
<p>Primary Actor:</p>	<p>Help Desk</p>
<p>Preconditions:</p>	<p>Collection manager is doing research about a certain topic to optimise the standard and variety of the library's collection.</p>
<p>Postconditions:</p>	<p>Collection manager receives valuable tips for research and realisation of the project.</p>
<p>Main Success Scenario:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collection manager gets in touch with the Help Desk of RESILIENCE. - Collection manager finds suitable sources. - Help Desk can assist the collection manager in connecting with experts in the subject area.
<p>Constraints/Issues/Risks:</p>	<p>Help desk cannot assist:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Help desk manager does not understand the collection manager's request. - Help desk cannot refer to experts on this topic, as there are none known in the RESILIENCE network. <p>Help desk assists, but it's not useful:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Help desk manager connects collection manager with several experts and libraries. But in the end these experts are not capable of the request of the collection manager.

Frequency of Use:	Whenever collection managers optimise their portfolios.
Status:	In Preparation.
Owner:	RESILIENCE WP2
Priority:	Medium

Table 7: Use Case Template Scientific Support/Empowerment

SMART Goal: The RESILIENCE Help Desk will be put in place in the next phase of RESILIENCE (2026-2028). This will be achieved in co-operation between WP2 and WP3 through the further evaluation of user needs for a helpdesk by WP3 and the resulting development of the necessary facilities for a helpdesk.

4. Conclusion and Next Steps

The use cases resulting from the user stories can be used efficiently to define user requirements and functional requirements for existing and future RESILIENCE services, as demonstrated in the examples above. Further objectives for the for the Preparatory Phase are summarised as follows:

1. Identify when new use cases can be developed in conjunction with new (in-kind) services.
2. Define a strategy, at what stage of the onboarding/implementation phase should use cases be produced in the service development and onboarding process.
3. Identify the most urgent (category of) services to be developed (according to the current data) in addition to the use cases presented here.
4. Include eight research-based use cases from the ITSERR⁹ project by M42 in the next batch of use cases. WP3 will accomplish this goal by analysing these use cases and their development conditions (i.e. the workshops and interviews) and adapting them to the RESILIENCE strategy. Achieving this goal will use and create synergy effects between the projects and will contribute to the collection of use cases (2nd batch).
5. For the refining and further development of archetypes, RESILIENCE WP3 will collaborate with the ITSERR project, which takes a similar approach to developing design personas to better understand behaviours and motivations, and identify the needs and pain points of different user types that will drive the design process.

⁹ [ITSERR: Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE](#).

5. Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	18/08/2022	GRANT AGREEMENT, Project: 101079792 — RESILIENCE PPP — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02
R2	31/08/2020	D2.3: High-Level User Strategy Report — Grant 871127 — RESILIENCE (RESILIENCE_WP2_USR_01.00_FINAL) [Confidential]
R3	31/10/2023	D3.5 User Stories Catalogue – 1st Batch
R4	29/02/2024	D3.1 Workshops Proceedings - 1st Batch
R5	24/01/2024	RESILIENCE's Vision and Mission Statement: Vision, Mission, and Values – Serving Research, Building Knowledge, Version 02.00

Funded by
the European Union